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Knowledge Technologies
for Democracy

KT4D Social Risk Toolkit Module A: AI, free will and autonomy – The impact of social networks and misinformation on citizens' opinions and attitudes

D3.1 MOD. A

December 2025

Funded by
the European Union

This document is part of the deliverable *KT4D Social Risk Toolkit - Modules A, B, and C (Version 1)* (2024) authored by Morisseau, T., & Lima, E., and accessible <https://zenodo.org/records/11491486>

Deliverable Abstract

The integration of artificial intelligence in multiple aspects of our daily lives poses a great challenge in shaping civic participation within societies. Effective civic engagement finds its foundation in the empowerment of citizens who actively participate in public discourse, and in the articulation of their viewpoints. Understanding the dynamics that underpin trust in democratic institutions in this new context is thus important.

Module A questions individuals' capacity to navigate AI-based content and recommendations while safeguarding their autonomy and free will. Module B examines the requisites for the utilisation of AI to preserve institutional trust. Indeed, the use of AI in a wide range of fields could generate situations that are, or are perceived to be, unfair, thereby threatening the social balance established between members of the same community. Module C puts the new challenges posed by technological transformations into perspective, by analysing historical precedents and how they have shaped culture and social interactions over centuries.

Through a comprehensive exploration and assessment, modules A, B and C of KT4D's Social Risk Toolkit will seek to address an important challenge: identify exactly where regulation is needed to ensure that AI benefits society as a whole, and identify the conditions for trust in social institutions, in order to guarantee effective public debate and societal choices are made by citizens themselves.

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The impact of social networks and misinformation on citizens' opinions and attitudes

The impact of social networks and artificial intelligence on citizens' opinions and attitudes is often framed in terms of manipulation, persuasion, and cognitive vulnerability. In public debates, AI-driven content generation and algorithmic curation are portrayed as major threats to individuals' ability to distinguish truth from falsehood and to form autonomous judgements. Such concerns, however, can only be properly assessed if they are grounded in a realistic understanding of how people process, evaluate, and use information in everyday contexts.

This section adopts a psychological and cognitive perspective on misinformation and disinformation, focusing on the interaction between cognitive biases, emotional motivations, social communication goals, and contemporary information environments. Rather than assuming passive belief formation, it examines why certain information is attractive, how engagement varies in depth, and under which conditions misleading content actually influences attitudes and behaviour. From this perspective, AI technologies are analysed not as a radical rupture, but as amplifiers of existing dynamics within social networks and public communication.

1. Psychological attractors

Neuroscience research has long shown that not only are we wired to be attracted to relevant stimuli, but information itself activates the reward system (Kang et al., 2009; Ligneul et al., 2018). A piece of information is all the more attractive as it possesses some cognitive appeal – and information can be crafted for that purpose (Acerbi, 2019a).¹ This involves elements of heightened social relevance and implications that enhance their cognitive attractiveness.

In the modern world, the variety of diverse foods has led to the widespread consumption of unhealthy diets, primarily due to the exploitation of human instincts, which historically associated taste with nutritional value. Similarly, AI-generated content may affect our information environment, making it more difficult to discern accurate information. Although the comparison to snack foods is limited, it remains useful to illustrate how changes in our environment can complicate our ability to understand reality.

1.1. Content-based appeal

Information can be attractive *per se* because it concerns aspects of reality that, if true, would have important implications for the self. If the information is plausible, and even if there is still a strong possibility that it is not true, its implications may be sufficiently interesting to be attended to.

Information is indeed more appealing to the human mind when it concerns central, relevant aspects of human life. This is the case for negative content (Bebbington et al., 2017), content related to threats (Blaine & Boyer, 2018), or disgusting content (Eriksson et al., 2016). The preference for negative stimuli – or negativity bias – has an evolutionary explanation, as individuals who better detect dangerous or negative elements of their environment are more likely to survive. Brain responses to

¹ False information can be manufactured based on features that make them attractive in an almost unconstrained way, whereas “true” news cannot, simply because they need to correspond to reality. False information can be intentionally crafted to propagate more extensively than accurate information.

sensory, cognitive, and motor stimuli are, in addition, more intense for negative stimuli (Ito et al., 1998).

Moreover, if such information is relevant to oneself, it is also relevant to others. It makes senders appear more competent than neutral or positive information (Boyer & Parren, 2015). On social media, alarmist headlines receive more attention than reassuring ones. In-lab experiments simulating real-world communication on social media confirm that, as information is passed from one individual to another, messages generally tend to become shorter and their content increasingly distorted, but risk-related information, on the contrary, is progressively exaggerated (Moussaïd, Brighton & Gaissmaier, 2015).

Another feature that increases the attractiveness of information is **when it is both sufficiently surprising and sufficiently plausible to resonate optimally with one's prior knowledge**. This aspect is related to a stream of research in cognitive anthropology (Boyer, 2007; Boyer & Bergstrom, 2008) that has looked at supernatural concepts in religious beliefs and has demonstrated that a concept is more likely to achieve a cognitive optimum in terms of cultural transmission if it violates a few intuitions while being otherwise consistent with the individual's model of the world. In the case of fake news, the information is often very surprising, but plausible enough (at least to some part of the population) to be shared with some success, i.e. to be accepted by others as valuable information.

Finally, more attention is generally paid to socially related content such as gossip, i.e., information about intense third-party social relationships (Mesoudi et al., 2006). More generally, the literature on cultural evolution suggests that social information tends to attract more attention and be more easily remembered than non-social information.

1.2. Explanatory power

Information can also be attractive because it contributes to a powerful explanatory framework, which, if true, would make better sense of reality. Making sense of reality is useful in taking action, and in general, we like information that has explanatory implications on aspects of the world that escape us (Lantian et al., 2020). Problem-solving is associated with pleasure and 'Aha!' moments (when we suddenly grasp the solution to a problem) promote the retention of memories. Similarly, superstition has been interpreted as an adaptive tendency to falsely detect the presence of a causal link, to avoid missing it when it turns out to be real (Beck & Forstmeier, 2007; Foster & Kokko, 2008; Shermer, 2022). It also predicts the perception of illusory control (Griffiths et al., 2019). Again, the bottom line is that the benefit of holding the information to be true outweighs the consequences of being wrong if it turns out to be false. A little bit of falsehood does not always make our models of the world unfit for our purposes (Cushman, 2020).

An intuitive way to explain why certain kinds of things happen is to see them as the result of intentional action. The literature on supernatural beliefs that we mentioned earlier emphasises that we are cognitively biased to detect intentionality wherever we look. This teleological bias makes us interpret information in a certain way (Wagner-Egger et al., 2018). Conspiracy theories exploit this tendency of the human mind to gain traction and be massively shared. Van Prooijen et al. (2018) conducted a study on the link between teleological and conspiratorial thinking. They showed that participants who were most likely to perceive patterns in a series of random coin flips or abstract paintings (e.g. Pollock's work) were also those most likely to subscribe to conspiracy theories and to develop conspiratorial thinking. This tendency to illusory pattern perception also predicts people's receptivity to pseudo-

profound bullshit, i.e. statements that appear to be very profound at first sight, but which are in fact meaningless (Walker et al., 2019).

It also appears that people are more likely to believe in conspiracy theories when they involve events that they feel the need to explain (Lantian et al., 2020). In addition, people are more attracted to conspiracy theories when important psychological needs are frustrated, for instance when feeling socially excluded (Graeupner & Coman 2017). Individuals with a strong need for uniqueness and for feeling special would also be more likely to value privileged access to secret information (Lantian et al., 2017), which is precisely what characterises conspiracy narratives. They foster a feeling of being able to understand the world in depth, to comprehend it from a global point of view rather than from a subjective and necessarily limited perspective. The need to feel unique would thus increase the tendency to believe in these theories. Besides, belief in fake news seems to be associated with various psychological dimensions such as delusion, dogmatism and religious fundamentalism (Bronstein et al., 2019).

Related to this need for explanation is the notion of **need for closure** (Kruglanski & Webster, 2018), which characterises an individual's tendency to consider an answer as definitive, i.e., to "seize and then freeze on early judgements". The scale developed by Roets & van Hiel (2007) includes items such as: "I don't like situations that are uncertain". This notion illustrates the importance for individuals to maintain a coherent knowledge system. This need for meaning can contribute to privileging straightforward information with strong explanatory power, at the expense of true information that is more complex and less relevant for the individual.

1.3. Reasons for emotional stances

Finally, **information can be attractive because it fosters the development of emotions and attitudes that we already hold**. In such cases, the truthfulness of the content may be less important than the emotion it induces, be it negative, such as anger or indignation, or positive, such as joy or pride. Whether the information is accurate does not really matter in such cases. Most important is the fact that the induced emotion can be justified and shared (Schaffner & Luks, 2018).

Baum, Frömer & Rahman (2020) specifically studied how emotions influence the perceived credibility of internet headlines featuring personalities unknown to participants. They show that emotionally-valenced titles elicited faster, more extreme, and more trusting judgements than neutral titles, including when they came from sources deemed to be unreliable. The measurement of pupil dilation (as a proxy for the attentive effort engaged) also varied with the emotional valence of the titles. This study confirms the central role of emotions in the way false information is evaluated on the internet.

2. Shallow vs. deep engagement with information

Information can be accepted while being only partially understood when it is being used not to derive consequences from its content but for other goals such as demonstrating affiliation or self-justification (Sperber, 2008).

From an individual's perspective, the utility of knowing the truthfulness of a particular fact is indeed limited and depends on the context. The importance of an accurate representation of reality depends on the intended use of the information – it may be crucial or just an added benefit. And **in many cases, shallow engagement with information is often sufficient**. Plausibility rather than certainty may be

sufficient, depending on one's particular purpose, whether for oneself or in communicating with others. **In such a context, there is no longer a strong epistemic barrier to misinformation.**

2.1. Sharing is not believing

There is no need to assume that misinformation is knowingly shared as such. The premise that so many people believe things that are so obviously false is a bit too puzzling. Do they genuinely endorse this information? If they don't, it would no longer be necessary to resort to the idea that people are generally extremely gullible. But what is the point in sharing information if you don't believe it?

Sharing information, whether in real life or on social networks, does not always have the function of directing others' attention to the facts of the matter. It can also be used to emphasise the relevance of an idea, and to illustrate a certain epistemic position. It can also be an indirect way of expressing an opinion or manifesting an attitude or an emotion. While some online players do indeed aim for outright disinformation (Elsawah & Howard, 2020), most people who share information on the Internet do not do so with the malicious intention of misleading others. Indeed, **conveying genuine information is not always the primary goal of communication**, especially when it comes to communication on the internet (Acerbi, 2019b). Again, we care about truth to the extent that it is relevant to us and to those with whom we are sharing the information.

Of course, false information may slip through the cracks of our epistemic vigilance, and we may accept information that we would have rejected if we had been more careful or informed. We do not want to be misled by knowledge that could harm us, nor do we want to be caught spreading false information, as we care for our reputation. Generally speaking, however, our vigilance adapts to the level of accuracy that fits our purposes.

The pragmatic use of language is an essential aspect of human communication and has evolved alongside it. As content can be produced and shared at minimal cost, for example by sharing an article without reading it, the sharing of information can be interpreted in many ways: as a way of conveying or approving its content, as a way of highlighting its existence, as sarcastic, as an attempt to impress others about the breadth of our information and knowledge, etc. We use the Internet to exchange views, opinions and attitudes. It can be used to signal a political or social affiliation (Osmundsen et al., 2021) or to share something fun or interesting (Acerbi, 2019a). A study by Berriche & Altay (2020) shows, for example, that most of the posts that were published on a scientific misinformation website were phatic posts, meant to create social bonds, and not to provide informational content. There is, also, a well-established gap between what people read in private and what they share on social networks to demonstrate their expertise (Bright, 2016).

Thus, content shared on social media does not carry a strong presumption of truthfulness. Several results support this interpretation. First, it seems that **people are not interested in the truthfulness of what they share**. The limited effects of the debunking techniques can be interpreted as pointing to the general irrelevance of truthfulness in this type of situation: the fact that people are sensitive to fact-checking and remembering that a given information has been debunked does not prevent them from sharing it. In addition, **people commonly share information without even reading it** (Gabelkov et al., 2016).

Even more striking are situations in which people advance patently false claims. Schaffner & Luks (2018), for example, showed a panel of participants two photographs of the respective inaugurations of Presidents Obama and Trump. While they were, otherwise, perfectly capable of discerning

differences in attendance, one in seven participants identified Trump's inauguration photo as having attracted the largest crowd, despite the evidence. How should this type of response, that is so obviously made in bad faith, be interpreted? Schaffner & Luks argue that expressing an opinion without sincerely believing it can be a way of showing support for a preferred political party or candidate. The respondents do know that this communicative behaviour will be interpreted as such (that is, not *literally*) by others, and they use it to impose their own political views, acting *as if* the information were true (Lynch, 2022).

2.2. On the whole, people are vigilant when it matters

Humans have developed special cognitive skills dedicated to monitoring information that comes from others (Sperber et al., 2010). The cultural intelligence hypothesis developed by Michael Tomasello and his colleagues (Herrmann et al., 2007) or Robin Dunbar's social brain hypothesis (Dunbar, 2009) suggest that the several intellectual faculties that are specific to humans compared to other closely related species can be explained by the need for people to collaborate within a group for their survival. This selective pressure would have favoured a set of socio-cognitive abilities during the evolution of the species conducive to optimal collaboration within social groups.

In particular, understanding the intentions of others is central to our ability to exchange information and to evolve socially within social groups. This ability to monitor in a fine-grained fashion when one should or shouldn't trust others develops very early in life. Developmental literature has shown how, even at a very young age, children do not regard all information as equally reliable and can distinguish between sources according to their skills and intentions (Clément, 2010; Harris, 2012). For example, by the age of two, children can tell whether a source is competent or not and whether she is acting in their best interests. By the age of three, they can discriminate between a well-informed and an ill-informed source on the topic at hand.

These different cues to a source's credibility can be classified into two broad categories: those that relate to the source's competence and knowledge (whether the source is in a position to know) and those that relate to the source's honesty (that is, their sincerity and willingness to say what they believe to be true). Generally speaking, the wide range of literature on credibility indicates that **a reliable source is a competent source whose intentions are aligned with our interests** (Pornpitakpan, 2004).

The match between the interests of the source and their audience is a fundamental aspect of epistemic trust. In some communicative situations, expectations about the honesty of the source will not focus on the literal truthfulness of their explicit assertion, but on the relevance of the implicit message. If what matters is the ability to defend one's own values, there is no need to scrutinise accuracy. People may thus accept doubtful information in one communicative context (e.g., when defending a political position) while later seeking true information in order to make an informed decision. Thus, **the reliability of a source in a given communicative context is assessed in light of one's own objectives.**

Sharing the same goals as the audience and making them explicit is therefore key in eliciting trust. We trust sources that we know will send us genuine information at a level that is adequate for what we want to use it for.

3. Challenges to the information environment

3.1. Fake news

For many scholars², the rise of digital communications and in particular social media is one of the main, if not the only, cause of a so-called 'infodemia'. Over the last decade, there has been a great deal of literature on the ease with which false information spreads, with some showing, for example, that "false information spreads six times faster than true information"(Vosoughi, Roy & Aral, 2018).³ Misinformation is not a recent concern, nor is it a social media phenomenon. It was present before the digital age (Altay, Berriche & Acerbi, 2023), and one can easily find examples of misinformation disseminated by traditional media such as newspapers and television. The essayist Jonathan Swift observed in 1710 that "it often happens that, if a lie be believed only for an hour, it hath done its work, and there is no further occasion for it. Falsehood flies, and truth comes limping after it."

The evidence suggesting that fake news and deliberate misinformation significantly change people's opinions is not particularly strong. In the United States, while many individuals do consume fake news, these individuals are predominantly those with strong partisan leanings, who seek out fake news that confirms their preconceptions, viewing it more as a form of entertainment rather than a catalyst for changing their views. To date, **research indicates that the overall amount of fake news circulating on social networks is minimal, comprising only about 2-3% of the total information** (Altay, Berriche & Acerbi, 2023). **This small percentage is largely consumed by individuals with extreme political views that align with the fake news content.** Fake news represents a very small percentage of the information consumed in the US (0.15% according to Allen et al., 2021) and 80% of total exposure to fake news can be attributed to a very small number (1%) of individuals (Grinberg et al., 2019). Particularly in a democracy, the informational environment is largely demand-driven. The prevalence of particular types of content is primarily due to public interest rather than deliberate attempts to influence people. Journalists and editors do have some agency in selecting which stories to cover, and how to cover them, but the overwhelming selection bias of the population plays a significant role. Journalists aim to write content that will attract readership. Therefore, the presence of fake news is often a reflection of pre-existing public demand and agreement with the content.

3.2. Deepfakes

Deepfakes – that is, videos that are manipulated using artificial intelligence to appear as though someone is saying or doing something they did not – constitute a more specific challenge. Some studies (e.g., Dobber et al., 2021) suggest that they can significantly influence political attitudes, especially when they are micro-targeted to specific demographic groups. Deepfakes would thus be a powerful mode of disinformation, along with other forms such as false news stories or trolling on social media platforms. For example, a deepfake video discrediting a political candidate can negatively affect people's attitudes towards both the politician and their associated party. Yet, other studies show that deepfakes are more effective when they are shown to demographic groups that are already

² "Post-truth" became the Oxford Dictionaries' Word of the Year in 2016.

³ This famous study by Vosoughi et al. showed that a small number of fake news stories can be highly influential and reach between 1,000 and 100,000 people. Yet, these figures need to be balanced against the potential dissemination of true information in general (not just of rumours that have been proven to be true) and the latter is, in fact, much more widely and rapidly disseminated (Acerbi, 2019).

personally interested in their content. Strong supporters of a candidate will disregard a deepfake video discrediting their candidate, due to their existing beliefs and loyalties.

While deepfakes are in some ways groundbreaking, they are a continuation of manipulation tactics that have existed for some time, including rhetoric, propaganda, and deceptive presentation of facts (Etienne, 2021). The narrative that deepfakes pose an unprecedented threat to information trustworthiness is not as solid as it seems. Deepfake technology is developing fast, but it is neither the first nor the most powerful tool to manipulate information. Deepfakes themselves are not the cause of a loss of trust among the public: distrust in political representatives and institutions predate this technology.

Instead of deepfakes contributing to a post-trust era, they might instead intensify existing scepticism or the erosion of trust, leveraging generalised distrust that already exists in society. Deepfakes could actually aid in the transition from instrumental rationality to social rationality by fostering a critical approach to information consumption and trust-building in the digital age. Just as societies learned to question the authenticity of photographs, the presence of deepfakes may teach people to develop a more critical and informed approach to digital content, encouraging the search for trustworthy sources of information.

The example of deepfake videos is revealing in that it shows the point at which belief in the truth of the information conveyed can actually be a problem. If someone cares about a particular issue (because there is a lot at stake for them), they will be more cautious.

3.3. Consequences for the economy of information

Of course, the proliferation of content generated by LLMs and other generative visual models is worrying. AI could indeed lower the quality of information online both by increasing people's ability to produce a lot of text, and by flooding the internet with false information and generate noise. Let's see how these new possibilities could lower the quality of available information.⁴

AI increases people's ability to produce a lot of text

Online content is often created with the intention of persuading individuals to accept particular points of view. Let's say a given AI system writes a massive number of articles, all arguing for some conclusion X. How can people trust the information that is being shared if an AI can produce any article in an instant? But there are also reasons to be optimistic.

There is indeed already an enormous amount of information on the internet. And the bottleneck is not how many articles there are on a given topic, because there is already far more than anyone will ever read. The production stage is already relatively cheap. One could hire someone to write an article. It will only cost them a few thousand dollars at most. Even if propagandists are more inclined to use ChatGPT to produce fake news and take advantage of the cost reduction, it will make a very small difference because the cost of writing articles is not the main cost anyway.

Rather, **the bottleneck is individual attention. It is how to get people to read them and take them seriously.** That bottleneck is largely controlled by the big players in the field: cable news, big newspapers (and to a lesser extent peers and colleagues and social networks). Getting more than a

⁴ <https://80000hours.org/podcast/episodes/hugo-mercier-misinformation-mass-persuasion/>

few hundred people to read it on Facebook costs a lot of money. Moreover, only 1% of the people who click on an article will actually read it in its entirety, which highlights the real constraint. The issue is not the quantity of content being produced but rather how much of it is actually being consumed. Even if there are thousands of articles on a particular topic, the likelihood of them being widely read remains low. There is little evidence to suggest that this trend will change significantly.

Also, LLMs might also help trustworthy institutions. They might not write important pieces of information by ChatGPT, but journalists might ask questions to LLMs to help them do other parts of their jobs, instead of writing the final piece.

AI floods the internet with false information and generates noise

AI could help generate an overwhelming amount of low-quality or misleading content, making it difficult for people to distinguish truth from falsehood. This strategy is already confusing people enough to make them distrust the entire information ecosystem. The primary concern is not necessarily that people will be persuaded by specific falsehoods, but that the sheer volume of misinformation will increase the overall noise in the information environment. This leads to a noisy internet filled with content that appears credible, making people sceptical of all information and leading to a general disinterest in checking facts or forming strong opinions.

Historically, some governments have employed similar strategies to control their populations by flooding the information space with noise and confusion. Such strategy prevents citizens from trusting any source of information, thereby disengaging them from public discourse. An example is the current scepticism around news regarding the Russian invasion of Ukraine, where propaganda from multiple sides, including through the use of deepfakes (see Box 5 “The case of deepfakes”), has led to a decrease in public efforts to understand the situation. **The spread of misinformation by official sources, such as governments, academics, or major newspapers, poses a significant risk.** Such instances of ‘official misinformation’ are particularly harmful as they carry more weight and have a wider reach. It is crucial to address this major issue to maintain public trust in authoritative sources. The prevalence of conspiracy theories is often linked to the level of corruption and mistrust in institutions, highlighting the importance of maintaining transparency and accountability. Moreover, the long-term impact of AI-generated content is uncertain, especially for future generations who will grow up in a world saturated with such content. Future generations may find it harder to distinguish between real and AI-generated information, unlike those with more established views of the world. This could lead to increased scepticism and reduced trust in information sources over time.

Yet, despite the proliferation of low-quality content, many people still rely on curated information from trusted sources. The credibility of the source remains a key factor in determining the reliability of information (Druckman, 2022). If established and trusted sources, such as reputable newspapers or well-regarded colleagues, continue to maintain their standards, the overall impact of AI-generated misinformation may be mitigated. The role of these curators is crucial in ensuring that information remains trustworthy, even in the midst of a flood of junk content. There are also good reasons to think that the demand for truthful information will ensure the persistence of reliable sources. As long as there is a demand for accuracy, institutions will likely continue to provide truthful content, supported by the need to maintain their reputation. Competition among multiple sources of information can help ensure that false information is called out and corrected, maintaining the integrity of the information ecosystem. The effectiveness of misinformation can therefore be countered if reliable institutions continue to function and maintain public trust. In authoritarian regimes, where the

government can control and flood the information space, credible private actors are often suppressed, making it easier to mislead the public. But in democratic societies with multiple sources of reliable information, it is more challenging for misinformation to take root extensively.

In conclusion, the proliferation of AI-generated content, with or without malicious intent, *can* play a major role in altering the quality of public debate. Not because people incorporate false information into their belief system, but because it may contribute to creating a climate of mistrust in institutions. The massive use by social networks of algorithms, designed to optimise user engagement, appears to be amplifying this phenomenon. Trusted sources and institutions thus remain central to mitigating its impact.

4. Does high personalisation make information more persuasive?

Algorithms are critical to the management of the vast amount of information available on social media platforms. When users access a social media news feed, they may be presented with hundreds or even thousands of stories from friends, followed pages, and sponsored content. Without some form of curation, identifying valuable information would be challenging.⁵ But the question is, how fine-tuned to people's previous behaviour should the selection be, while still preserving people's autonomy?

Personalisation can significantly enhance the persuasiveness of messages. By tailoring content to individual tastes and preferences, it is possible to create highly engaging experiences, whether for entertainment or information. AI can enable behavioural interventions to be more personalised and contextual for individual consumers by accounting for their unique traits and the specific environments they are in. Combining usage data (created when people use online services) with personal data (relating to an identifiable person), makes it possible to draw up extremely precise files on individuals, their tastes, their interests, and so on. They can be given a personalised pitch for a target message based on their existing views and personality: in theory, they could be given the arguments that are most persuasive to them, given their pre-existing beliefs. AI systems, particularly LLMs, thus have the potential to become extraordinarily persuasive. These systems could outperform human persuasion by producing highly engaging content.

4.1. Limits to AI persuasiveness

Having access to a custom-made series that perfectly aligns with one's interests can indeed be extremely satisfying, and this can lead to interventions that are more effective, and sometimes more equitable. However, **when multiple sources compete for attention using personalised content, it becomes difficult for any single viewpoint to dominate or stand out.**

People also consume content – whether it is news, fiction, or other types of media – not only for personal enjoyment, but also because they want to be able to talk to others about it. Much of the power of persuasive media lies in its ability to be shared and discussed within communities, thereby amplifying its impact. **If a given content is proposed to a single person because it is highly personalised, it may also fail to resonate broadly.** Lack of shared experience could then diminish its value and reduce the motivation to consume it in the first place. In fact, previous research has shown

⁵ The diffusion of the printing press generated a comparable panic, with intellectuals worried the world would “fall into a state as barbarous as that of the centuries that followed the fall of the Roman Empire.” (Adrian Ballet, 1685).

that much persuasion comes from people being convinced by the media or government, and then passing that knowledge or belief on to others (Aarøe, 2011).

Finally, the fact that AI can help find very strong arguments is not necessarily a problem in itself. **If AI systems could create highly engaging content, such increased engagement could also benefit fact-checked and reliable content**, making true information more appealing than fake news. Given that people are already more exposed to reliable news, increasing the engagement of true information could have a positive impact.

But the real bottleneck to influence remains the amount of attention people are willing to pay. Individuals have limited attentional capacity, and simply cannot pay attention to every issue, which limits the potential impact of even the most persuasive content. The idea that AI could ever persuade people of anything is thus not very plausible. AI's persuasiveness is likely to peak at levels barely surpassing the most charismatic and persuasive humans. The main limiting factor is attention; complex arguments require time and sustained focus, which humans are generally unwilling to invest. Even if an AI could write an exceptionally persuasive book, it is unlikely to change many minds if only a few people read it. Moreover, as people become aware of the potential for AI to create persuasive content, they will also become more critical and less easily swayed.

4.2. What does make communication more persuasive

Significant opinion changes occur through sustained exposure to arguments and evidence, often conveyed by trusted individuals. Historical shifts in public opinion on issues like gay marriage or trans rights have largely resulted from generational changes and persistent discussions within social networks (Kiley & Vaisey, 2020). Personal experiences and conversations with friends, family, and colleagues have a greater impact on changing opinions than impersonal media.

For instance, direct experiences, such as meeting someone from a marginalised group, can be more persuasive than any written argument. Discussions in a familiar environment, where there is trust, are more likely to lead to a change of opinion. While indirect influences, such as media consumption, play a role, meaningful and repeated discussions are crucial for large-scale opinion shifts.

Despite the potential of AI to enhance argumentation quality, the main challenge remains scaling meaningful discussions. Efforts like canvassing, where people engage in conversations about important issues – e.g., Kalla & Broockman (2020) – have shown some success in changing attitudes. However, replicating this on a large scale is difficult. **Effective persuasion requires trust, empathy, and meaningful exchanges, which are challenging to achieve through impersonal AI-generated content alone.**

The references mentioned in this report are available in the Bibliography of KT4D Social Risk Toolkit Module A: AI, free will and autonomy. <https://zenodo.org/records/18374167>

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